

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Active set prediction for nonlinear model predictive control on a shrinking horizon based on the principle of optimality

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Summary

We provide insights into the structure of the set of active constraints arising for optimal solutions to nonlinear model predictive control problems along a shrinking horizon. The principle of optimality combined with a particular order of the constraints allows the prediction of the future active sets without solving the corresponding optimization problem. By describing the development of optimal active sets along a shrinking horizon, we state an important relationship for transferring ideas such as dynamic programming approaches from the linear to the nonlinear case. We further use the information about active and inactive constraints to rearrange and remove constraints of the original nonlinear program as described in previous work and thus simplify the problem. Numerical experiments show for the problem class treated here that the inherent robustness coming with the regional characteristic of the active sets with respect to the state space makes this approach useful also if uncertainties are present.

KEYWORDS:

Nonlinear Model Predictive Control, Active Sets, Optimal Control, Shrinking Horizon

1 | INTRODUCTION

Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (nonlinear MPC, NMPC) can handle constraints, nonlinear system dynamics, and multiple inputs and outputs.^{1,2} As it requires to solve, in every time step, a nonlinear program (NLP) predicting the system behavior for a certain horizon length, the computational complexity of this control approach can be demanding, if not restrictive.

Several approaches for reducing the computational effort of NMPC have been investigated. Focusing on the solution algorithm, approaches as presented in, e.g., References 3, 4 accelerate in particular the solution process of the NLP. Another class of approaches focuses on exploiting information about the structure of the solution. This class contains nonlinear variants of the explicit MPC approach for linear systems^{5,6}, such as, e.g., approximations of the explicit solution^{7,8}, region-free approaches⁹, and encompasses robust variants^{10,11}. Further approaches of this class use, e.g., only partial information about the explicit solution to provide locally optimal feedback laws¹², or they exploit the nonincreasing properties of the Lyapunov cost function to identify and remove inactive constraints before solving the NLP¹³. Another promising field receiving a lot of attention is the combination of MPC with machine learning methods, assisting, among others, in modeling the prediction model or constructing the NLP (see, e.g., Ref. 14 for an overview).

Recently, for linear MPC problems, Reference 15 provided insight into the structure of the set of all active sets, i.e., the sets of constraints that are active for an optimal solution. It was shown that for a given active set and under mild conditions, the development of this active set for the same optimization problem is known also along an increasing horizon length. These

insights directly evolved into a novel dynamic programming approach¹⁶ for the fast computation of explicit MPC solutions. In combination with the principle of optimality (see, e.g., Ref. 17, chapter 1.3), the results of Reference 15 also allow predicting the active set for the subsequent time step without solving the corresponding MPC problem. This was exploited in Reference 18 to predict the optimal polytope and corresponding control law as part of the explicit solution for a regional MPC approach to avoid the online solution of the underlying optimization problem.

For linear MPC, the relation between the active sets for different horizon lengths as described in Reference 15 is based on the fact that the finite- and infinite-horizon optimization problem are equal whenever the terminal constraints are inactive if the largest possible terminal set and the terminal penalty matrix resulting from solving the discrete-time algebraic Riccati equation are used (see, e.g., Ref. 19, see also Ref. 15). However, this property cannot easily be extended to NMPC, among other reasons because the unconstrained optimal feedback law and the terminal set can typically only be approximated in the nonlinear case using a linearized model (see, e.g., Ref. 1, 20). Thus, the extension of the results presented in References 15, 16, and 18 to the nonlinear case is a current field of research.

In Reference 21, we constructed candidate active sets for the current time step based on the previous solution before solving the NMPC problem. For the proof of recursive feasibility, it is essential that an open-loop feasible solution for the current time step can be constructed using the optimal solution of the previous one (see, e.g., Ref. 1). We transferred this idea to the development of active sets in Reference 21 and showed that under mild conditions, the construction of an active set that is indeed optimal for the current time step is possible for the majority of initial states. Further, we proposed to use the *a priori* information about active and inactive constraints to rearrange and remove constraints before solving the NLP. Since active sets are in general valid for a set of states, we also showed that this regional characteristic, which was already discussed in Reference 18, leaves the approach beneficial even if disturbances are present. Thus, Reference 21 was a first attempt to transfer the results of Reference 18 to the nonlinear case.

Besides the receding horizon approaches, NMPC approaches with shrinking horizon lengths have also received a lot of attention in both, application and theory. Typical applications for predictive control approaches and thus also for approaches with shrinking horizon lengths are problems arising in the chemical industry, such as, e.g., batch processes^{22,23}. Newer applications of NMPC on a shrinking horizon often include so-called *rendezvous* or *touchdown* problems. In References 24 and 25, the landing of reusable launch vehicles or the landing of a helicopter on a ship, respectively, is realized using shrinking horizon NMPC. The rendezvous and docking of spacecrafts is described in Reference 26. Further, in Reference 27, a combination of move blocking and switching parametrizations is used on a shrinking horizon for the control of an electric train, while Reference 28 presents a robust, self-triggered variant of shrinking horizon NMPC. Another robustification approach is proposed in Reference 29, which applies a variant of the well-known multi-stage NMPC scheme to the control along a shrinking horizon. The authors in Reference 30 perform dynamic programming on a shrinking horizon to deal with computational complexity.

The main contribution of this paper is to reveal that, based on the principle of optimality, the structure of the active sets is also known for NMPC when the prediction horizon is shrinking. We thus prove parts of the results in Reference 15, where the structure of the active sets for linear MPC problems was described, to be also applicable to the nonlinear case. Besides providing structural insights into the development of the active sets, we also discuss the robustness of the active set predictions based on their regional characteristic when disturbances apply. Further, as in Reference 21, where candidate active sets are constructed based on the previous ones, we apply the idea of rearranging and removing constraints predicted to be active and inactive and introduce an adapted algorithm for shrinking horizon NMPC to simplify the optimization problem before solving it.

Section 2 introduces the problem class and some preliminaries. The main contribution of this paper, i.e., the structure of active sets along a shrinking horizon, is presented in Section 3.1, followed by a discussion of its robustness in Section 3.2. Based on these results, the implementation of an approach to simplify NLPs is presented in Section 3.3. A computational study is presented in Section 4, and Section 5 gives an outlook on future work.

2 | PROBLEM CLASS AND PRELIMINARIES

We address nonlinear, discrete-time systems

$$x(k+1) = f(x(k), u(k)) + w(k), \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, \quad (1)$$

with $x(k) \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $u(k) \in \mathbb{R}^m$, and $w(k) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ denoting states, inputs, and disturbances, respectively, and we assume $f : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, with $f(0, 0) = 0$, to be twice continuously differentiable.

We solve the following NLP in every time step and for a certain horizon N to regulate system (1) to a region around the origin

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{X,U} V_f(x(N)) + \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \ell(x(k), u(k)) \\ \text{s.t. } & x(k+1) = f(x(k), u(k)), \quad k = 0, \dots, N-1 \\ & u(k) \in \mathcal{U}, \quad k = 0, \dots, N-1, \\ & x(k) \in \mathcal{X}, \quad k = 0, \dots, N-1, \\ & x(N) \in \mathcal{T}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The given current state $x(0)$ of every time step is used as an initial state. The decision variables read $X = (x^\top(1), \dots, x^\top(N))^\top$ and $U = (u^\top(0), \dots, u^\top(N-1))^\top$. The constraints on states and inputs are denoted by sets \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{U} , respectively, which are defined by a finite number of inequalities. We assume \mathcal{X} , \mathcal{U} to be compact and convex sets and to contain the origin in their interior. The horizon N shrinks with every time step k , i.e., $N = \hat{N} - \hat{k}$ where $\hat{k} = 0, \dots, \hat{N} - 1$ is the actual time step and \hat{N} is some starting horizon length. In $V_f(x) = x^\top P x$ and $\ell(x, u) = x^\top Q x + u^\top R u$, weighting matrices P , Q , and R are positive definite matrices of the obvious dimensions. We assume the terminal set $\mathcal{T} \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ with $0 \in \text{int}\mathcal{T}$ and the terminal cost function V_f together with an appropriate terminal control law on $\text{int}\mathcal{T}$ fulfill the stability properties summarized, e.g., in Reference 1, A1-A4. Note that the terminal set applied here is in general an approximation of the largest possible terminal set. Chosen as an ellipsoidal set, the terminal set $\mathcal{T} = \{x | x^\top P x \leq \gamma\}$ here defines only one additional constraint for (2).

The disturbance $w(k)$ in (1) is excluded from the prediction model used in (2), i.e., the disturbance is not part of the optimization problem. However, as we will show in Section 3.2, the set of constraints that are active for solving (2) in general belongs to the optimal solution for a set of states, i.e., one or more regions in the state space. The structure of the solution thus provides a certain robustness with respect to additive disturbances, since the same active set often results for the optimal solution even if the state deviates from the predicted one. Here, we exploit this form of inherent robustness mentioned, e.g., in References 18 and 21, to simplify the NLP *despite* additive disturbances.

By introducing the augmented decision variable $z = (X^\top, U^\top)^\top$, we can state problem (2) in a more compact fashion

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_z z^\top H z \\ \text{s.t. } & F(x(0), z) = 0 \\ & G(x(0), z) \leq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

with $H > 0$, $H \in \mathbb{R}^{N(n+m) \times N(n+m)}$, and

$$F(x(0), z) := \begin{pmatrix} x(1) - f(x(0), u(0)) \\ \vdots \\ x(N) - f(x(N-1), u(N-1)) \end{pmatrix},$$

i.e., F contains the predicted state trajectory resulting from $x(0)$ and some input sequence U . Since sets \mathcal{X} , \mathcal{U} , and \mathcal{T} are assumed to be defined by a finite number of inequalities in states and inputs, we summarize all inequalities depending on $x(0)$ and z as $G(x(0), z) \leq 0$. We further assume, without restriction, these inequalities to be ordered stagewise following the scheme

$$\begin{aligned} & x(0) \in \mathcal{X}, \quad u(0) \in \mathcal{U} \\ & x(1) \in \mathcal{X}, \quad u(1) \in \mathcal{U} \\ & \vdots \\ & x(N-1) \in \mathcal{X}, \quad u(N-1) \in \mathcal{U} \\ & x(N) \in \mathcal{T}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Note that problem (3) represents a compact formulation of (2) for a certain horizon N , i.e., H , F , and G change whenever the horizon changes.

A constraint $i \in \mathcal{Q}$, $\mathcal{Q} = \{1, \dots, q\}$ is called active if $G_i(x(0), z^*) = 0$, and inactive otherwise, i.e., if $G_i(x(0), z^*) < 0$, with index i referring to a certain line of matrix G , i.e., a certain inequality constraint. The indices of active (inactive) constraints are collected in the active set \mathcal{A} (inactive set \mathcal{I}). Further, we follow the notation in Reference 15 and express active sets also as bit

tuple with

$$\alpha_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i \in \mathcal{A} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}.$$

Thus, for Example 1 in Section 4.1 with $n = 2$ states and $m = 1$ inputs, a horizon length of $N = 3$, and constraints ordered as in (4), the active set $\mathcal{A} = \{3, 17, 19\}$ can be stated as

$$\alpha = \underbrace{001000}_{\substack{x(0) \in \mathcal{X}, \\ u(0) \in \mathcal{U}}} . \underbrace{000000}_{\substack{x(1) \in \mathcal{X}, \\ u(1) \in \mathcal{U}}} . \underbrace{000010}_{\substack{x(2) \in \mathcal{X}, \\ u(2) \in \mathcal{U}}} . \underbrace{1}_{x(N) \in \mathcal{T}} \quad (5)$$

where stages corresponding to one time step are separated by a dot. The concatenation of two tuples α^a and α^b is written as $\alpha^a \alpha^b$.

Let the feasible set \mathcal{F} be the set of all states for which a solution to (3) exists. We use the term 'full NLP' when referring to a regular NLP as in (3) to distinguish it from the 'simplified NLP' introduced in Section 3.3. The number of constraints on states (except for $x(N)$) and inputs for one time step are denoted by $q_{\mathcal{X}}$ and $q_{\mathcal{U}}$, respectively. If not stated explicitly, the term 'optimal' will refer to a local optimum of the nonconvex optimization problem.

3 | ACTIVE SET PREDICTION ON SHRINKING HORIZONS

We first describe how active sets change as the horizon shrinks. The patterns of these changes can then be used to predict sequences of active sets that occur for the NMPC-controlled system. Before stating an NMPC algorithm that is based on this idea, we discuss the robustness of the active set predictions.

3.1 | Structure of active sets

If a solution to (2) (or, equivalently, (3)) and the corresponding active set for horizon N are known and no disturbance or plant-model mismatch is assumed, we immediately know the active set for the nominal successor state and horizon $N - 1$ as well. This is stated more precisely in Reference 15, Prop. 1 for the linear case. We state this proposition here and show in the proof that this result for a shrinking horizon also holds for the nonlinear, nonconvex case.

Proposition 1. Consider the optimal control problem (3) for horizons $N - 1$ and N . Assume without restriction the constraints are ordered as in (4). Then, for every active set α_N of the problem with horizon N , there exists an active set α_{N-1} for the problem with horizon $N - 1$ such that

$$\alpha_N = \alpha \alpha_{N-1} \quad (6)$$

for some α of length $q_{\mathcal{X}} + q_{\mathcal{U}}$.

Proof. The claim follows from the principle of optimality (see, e.g., Ref. 17, chapter 1.3). Let $X_N^* = (x_N^{*\top}(1), \dots, x_N^{*\top}(N))^\top$, $U_N^* = (u_N^{*\top}(0), \dots, u_N^{*\top}(N-1))^\top$ be an optimal state and input sequence, respectively, resulting from solving problem (2) for horizon N and initial condition $x(0)$. Then, based on the principle of optimality,

$$\begin{aligned} X_{N-1}^* &= (x_{N-1}^{*\top}(1), \dots, x_{N-1}^{*\top}(N-1))^{*T} = (x_N^{*\top}(2), \dots, x_N^{*\top}(N))^\top, \\ U_{N-1}^* &= (u_{N-1}^{*\top}(0), \dots, u_{N-1}^{*\top}(N-2))^{*T} = (u_N^{*\top}(1), \dots, u_N^{*\top}(N-1))^\top \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

is an optimal solution to (2) for horizon $N - 1$ and initial condition $x(0) = x_N^*(1)$ (see also, e.g., Ref. 31, Sect. 5.1). Thus, the former initial state $x_N(0)$ and input $u_N(0)$ vanish for horizon $N - 1$. Since the constraints are assumed to be ordered as in (4), constraints for horizon N referring to stage $k = 0$, i.e., constraints on $x_N(0)$ and $u_N(0)$, appear on the very left of the bit tuple, i.e., α in $\alpha_N = \alpha \alpha_{N-1}$. With the horizon shrinking from N to $N - 1$, these are the first to vanish, such that α_{N-1} remains for horizon $N - 1$. \square

Proposition 1 yields an optimal solution and the corresponding active set for the nominal successor state on the shrinking horizon. Note that, since local and global minima may appear in the case of nonconvex optimization problems as addressed in this work, a different optimal solution may exist for horizon $N - 1$ compared to the locally optimal tail resulting from deleting the first stage of the solution for horizon N . However, statement (6) still holds for a local minimum.

For linear MPC, Corollary 2 in Reference 15 describes the development of active sets along a shrinking horizon in terms of bit tuples as described in (5). This Corollary holds also for nonlinear MPC problems, which we claim without proof because the proof provided in Reference 15 carries over to the nonlinear case.

Corollary 1 (see Ref. 15). Consider (2) (or, equivalently, (3)) for horizon N and assume the constraints to be ordered as in (4) without restriction. Let α_N be an arbitrary active set and partition α_N according to

$$\alpha_N = \underbrace{\alpha_{N,0}}_{q_N+q_U} \cdot \cdots \cdot \underbrace{\alpha_{N,N-1}}_{q_N+q_U} \cdot \underbrace{\alpha_{N,N}}_{q_T} \quad (8)$$

Let $x(0)$ be an arbitrary initial condition that results in the active set α_N and let $x^*(k)$, $k \geq 0$ refer to the optimal solution for $x(0)$. Then, for all $l \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}$, the active set

$$\alpha_{N-l} = \alpha_{N,l} \cdot \cdots \cdot \alpha_{N,N}$$

defines an optimal solution for (2) (or, equivalently, (3)) with horizon $N-l$ and initial condition $x^*(l)$.

By using notation (8), we can observe the following development of the optimal active set resulting from Corollary 1, again for Example 1 with the active set from (5), i.e., $\mathcal{A} = \{3, 17, 19\}$, and starting from $N = 3$

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_N &= 001000.000000.000010.1 & N &= 3 \\ \alpha_N &= 000000.000010.1 & N &= 2 \\ \alpha_N &= 000010.1 & N &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

By deleting the first stage, i.e., the bit tuples corresponding to the constraints on $x(0)$ and $u(0)$, we can directly determine the active set for time step $k+1$ and $N-1$. While the principle of optimality is well established and was already used in the context of open-loop optimal input signals, we extend its usability here to the prediction of active sets that are optimal for one or more regions in the state space. The inherent robustness coming along with this regional characteristic will be described in detail in Section 3.2.

3.2 | Inherent robustness

For a receding horizon, References 18 and 21 present approaches to predict active sets for the linear and nonlinear case, respectively, and provide a discussion on the inherent robustness resulting from the regional characteristic of active sets. We need to discuss this property also for the shrinking horizon case presented here.

The results of Section 3.1 are valid for the nominal case only. In fact, if no disturbances are present, Proposition 1 states that the open-loop optimal solution to (3) and the resulting corresponding active set for horizon N include the optimal solution and corresponding active set for horizon $N-1$. Obviously, if disturbances are present, open- and closed-loop solutions on the shrinking horizon may deviate.

However, in contrast to the optimal solution itself, an active set determined for some initial state $x(0)$ is in general valid not only for the point $x(0)$ but for an entire region of states. This regional characteristic may compensate for disturbances since there is a chance that the disturbed state will still be part of the region resulting in the same active set. For the linear case, the whole feasible set can be divided into an explicit solution of unique and convex polytopes, each of them resulting for a certain active set (see, e.g., Ref. 5, 32). For the nonlinear case, the regions that correspond to a certain active set in general result in nonlinearly bounded regions (see, e.g., Ref. 12). Figure 1 shows approximated regions for Example 1 of Section 4.1 summarizing states that result in the same active set along a solution for the first three time steps, i.e., $N = 7, 6, 5$. Note that the regions in Figure 1 are overlapping. Basically, Figure 1 shows three different state spaces, i.e., pointwise solutions resulting in the same active set for horizon $N = 7$ (cyan), $N = 6$ (red), and $N = 5$ (green), which explains the visual overlapping of the regions.

Due to the nonconvexity of (3), which again leads to nonconvex regions as shown in Figure 1, the described robustness coming with the regional characteristic is hard to quantify, since it would require excessive computational effort to characterize all regions of states that result in the same active set. However, we will show in the results in Section 4 that in more than 99% of all cases, an optimal solution with the predicted active set existed.

FIGURE 1 Regions for Example 1 summarizing states resulting in the same active set for the shrinking horizon NMPC scheme starting with initial state $x(0) = (1.1179, -0.9314)$ and $N = 7$ (cyan), $N = 6$ (red), and $N = 5$ (green). The regions result from solving problem (3) pointwise on a grid. The terminal set \mathcal{T} is sketched in white.

3.3 | Simplified nonlinear programs

By applying Corollary 1, we can determine the sets of active and inactive constraints for the subsequent time step and horizon $N - 1$ without solving an NLP. Thus we can use the information about active and inactive constraints for the current time step and horizon length N to reduce the complexity of the NLP to be solved for the next time step and horizon $N - 1$. Here, we propose to apply the approach presented in Reference 21 to simplify the NLP before solving it. The approach is based on rearranging and removing constraints according to the predicted active and inactive sets. Note that simply applying the predicted inputs along the shrinking horizon would lead to a loss of optimality due to the disturbances. In contrast, by applying the approach described in this section, we are able to react to the disturbances by solving a simplified optimization problem and thus preserve optimality of the input.

We first recall Proposition 1 in Reference 13 for problem (3) describing the influence of inactive constraints on the optimal solution.

Proposition 2 (see Ref. 13). Let $x(0) \in \mathcal{F}$ be arbitrary. Assume some or all of the inactive constraints are known before solving (3) and collect the indices of these constraints in $\tilde{\mathcal{I}}$. Then z^* is a solution to

$$\min_z z^\top H z \quad (9)$$

$$\text{s.t. } F(x(0), z) = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$G_{Q \setminus \tilde{\mathcal{I}}}(x(0), z) \leq 0 \quad (11)$$

if and only if it is a solution to (3).

Knowing the active and inactive sets in advance, we exploit the insight provided by Proposition 2 and remove inactive constraints (i.e., $G_{\tilde{\mathcal{I}}}(x(0), z)$) from the NLP (3). Further, we add constraints known to be active (i.e., $G_{\mathcal{A}}(x(0), z)$) as equality constraints. We state this more precisely in the following proposition and introduce the resulting algorithm afterward.

Proposition 3. Let $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ be the active set resulting from the previous time step according to Corollary 1, and let \tilde{z}^* denote, for the current state $\tilde{x}(0)$, the solution to the simplified NLP

$$\begin{aligned}
& \min_z \tilde{z}^\top H \tilde{z} \\
& \text{s.t. } F(\tilde{x}(0), \tilde{z}) = 0 \\
& \quad G_{\tilde{\mathcal{A}}}(\tilde{x}(0), \tilde{z}) = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

that results from rearranging the constraints corresponding to $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ and removing constraints corresponding to $\tilde{\mathcal{I}} = Q \setminus \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$. Let $G(\tilde{x}(0), \tilde{z}^*) \leq 0$ hold. Then \tilde{z}^* is a solution to (3) with $z^* = \tilde{z}^*$ and $x(0) = \tilde{x}(0)$.

Proof. Since inactive constraints do not influence the optimal solution according to Proposition 2, and none of the original constraints were violated by \tilde{z}^* by assumption, problems (3) and (12) are equivalent with respect to $\tilde{x}(0)$ and \tilde{z}^* . \square

Note that Proposition 3 allows a stronger simplification than Proposition 2. Since the constraint removal approach in Reference 13 only allows to detect a subset of constraints that are known to be inactive, the remaining constraints in (9), i.e., $G_{Q \setminus \tilde{\mathcal{I}}}(x(0), z) \leq 0$, can be both active and inactive. By predicting the active set as proposed in this article, however, only the constraints predicted to be active remain as equality constraints, i.e., $G_{\tilde{\mathcal{A}}}(\tilde{x}(0), \tilde{z}) = 0$ as in (12).

We expect to determine an optimal solution with this active set even if disturbances are present since there exists some probability that a disturbed successor state $\tilde{x}(k+1)$ will still be part of the same region of states resulting in the predicted optimal active set $\mathcal{A}(x(k+1))$ (see Fig. 1).

While the simplified NLP can result in exactly the same input signal as for a full NLP, i.e., as in the classic shrinking horizon NMPC approach, an optimal solution for problem (12) may also deviate from the one we would derive from solving (3). In general, several local minima can exist for the nonconvex problem class treated here. Further, disturbances, the chosen solution algorithm, or the initial guess provided to the solver may cause the optimizer to run into another optimum.

To ensure both, optimality and feasibility of a solution to (12), we need to check if an optimizer z^* resulting for the simplified NLP (12) respects the originally posed inequality constraints in (3), i.e., if $G(x(0), z^*) \leq 0$ holds as assumed in Proposition 3. As long as a solution to problem (12) exists and no constraints are violated, at least local optimality of the input signal is preserved, and we can apply the optimal solution resulting for (12) to the system. Note that, since the inequality constraints predicted to be active were still part of problem (12), technically it is sufficient to check only those constraints that have been removed from the NLP.

The resulting control strategy based on Proposition 3 for shrinking horizon NMPC is summarized in Algorithm 1, for an NMPC control starting with horizon \hat{N} and initial state $x(0)$. We solve problem (3) for the first time step and thus the starting horizon \hat{N} , and determine the optimal active set (line 2). In all subsequent time steps, we first update the active set according to Corollary 1, and solve the simplified NLP (12) (lines 4-7). If the resulting solution fulfills the original constraints posed on the NMPC problem, the optimal input $u^*(0)$ is applied to the system (lines 8-9). Only if at least one of the inequality constraints in (3), summarized by $G(x(0), z) \leq 0$, is violated or the problem is found infeasible, we solve the full NLP (3) for the current horizon N (line 11) as a backup and determine a new active set \mathcal{A} for the subsequent time steps.

Algorithm 1 Simplified inherently robust NMPC scheme on a shrinking horizon exploiting the structure of active sets

- 1: **Input:** \hat{N} , $x(0)$.
 - 2: Solve (3) for $x(0)$ and $N = \hat{N}$, determine \mathcal{A} , apply $u^*(0)$, and update $x(0)$
 - 3: **for all** $k = 1 \dots \hat{N} - 1$ **do**
 - 4: Set $N = \hat{N} - k$
 - 5: Update \mathcal{A} by deleting the first stage
 - 6: Rearrange active constraints, remove inactive constraints
 - 7: Solve (12) for current $x(0)$
 - 8: **if** Solution to (12) exists and $G(x(0), z^*) \leq 0$ **then**
 - 9: Apply $u^*(0)$, update $x(0)$
 - 10: **else**
 - 11: Solve (3), apply $u^*(0)$, update $x(0)$, determine \mathcal{A}
 - 12: **end if**
 - 13: **end for**
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4 | COMPUTATIONAL STUDY

We investigate both, the robustness of the active set prediction with respect to additive disturbances, and the reduction of the computational effort resulting for Algorithm 1 for two example systems. We first introduce the example systems. Afterward, we analyze the number of solved simplified and full NLPs and the average number of iterations required to find an optimal solution for both, a classic shrinking horizon NMPC scheme and the method introduced in Section 3.3.

4.1 | Example 1: Bilinear second-order system

The first example is a typical discrete-time benchmark system, bilinear in x and u , and was analyzed, e.g., in Reference 12

$$\begin{aligned} x_1(k+1) &= x_1(k) + 0.1x_2(k) + 0.1(0.5 + 0.5x_1(k))u(k) \\ x_2(k+1) &= x_2(k) + 0.1x_1(k) + 0.1(0.5 - 2.0x_2(k))u(k). \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

State and input constraints are defined as

$$-2 \leq x_{1,2}(k) \leq 2, \quad -2 \leq u(k) \leq 2,$$

for all k , respectively. The lower and upper bound on the disturbance $w(k)$ in (1) are chosen to $-10^{-2} \leq w_{1,2}(k) \leq 10^{-2}$, i.e., 0.5% of the lower and upper bounds on the state. Weighting matrices $Q = \text{diag}(0.05, 0.05)$ and $R = 0.1$ as well as the terminal penalty matrix P and the ellipsoidal terminal set \mathcal{T} are chosen as in Reference 12

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} 5.9353 & 5.2774 \\ 5.2774 & 5.9353 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathcal{T} = \{x \in \mathcal{X} \mid x^T P x \leq \gamma\}, \text{ with } \gamma = 0.0606.$$

4.2 | Example 2: Laboratory helicopter test bench

As a second example, we consider the discrete-time model with $n = 4$ states and $m = 2$ inputs resulting for a laboratory helicopter test bench by following the steps as described in Reference 33

$$\begin{aligned} x_1(k+1) &= x_1(k) + h x_2(k) & x_2(k+1) &= x_2(k) + h [c_1 \cos(x_1(k) + c_2) + c_3 \sin(x_1(k) + c_2) \\ & & & + c_4 x_2(k) + c_5(u_1(k) + u_2(k) + 2c_6) \cos(x_3(k))] \\ x_3(k+1) &= x_3(k) + h x_4(k) & x_4(k+1) &= x_4(k) + h [c_7 \sin(x_3(k)) + c_8 x_4(k) + c_9(u_1(k) + u_2(k))], \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

with sampling time $h = 0.25$ seconds and system parameters c_i , $i = 1, \dots, 9$ as summarized in Table 1.

The constraints are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} -6 \leq x_1(k) \leq 6, \quad -3 \leq x_{2,4}(k) \leq 3, \quad -4 \leq x_3(k) \leq 4, \\ -3 \leq u_{1,2}(k) \leq 7, \quad -10^{-3} \leq w_i(k) \leq 10^{-3}, \quad i = 1, \dots, 4 \end{aligned}$$

for all k . The disturbances thus range between approximately $\pm 0.033\%$ of the upper bound on $x_3(k)$. We apply the weighting matrices $Q = \text{diag}(1, 1, 1, 1)$ and $R = \text{diag}(0.1, 0.1)$. As in Reference 33, we also apply the terminal penalty matrix

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} 5.0263 & 2.0537 & 0 & 0 \\ 2.0537 & 3.8037 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 5.2487 & 1.4596 \\ 0 & 0 & 1.4596 & 1.7768 \end{pmatrix}$$

and the terminal set defined by $\mathcal{T} = \{x \in \mathcal{X} \mid x^T P x \leq \gamma\}$, with $\gamma = 2.522$.

4.3 | Simulation results

For each example and 500 randomly chosen, feasible initial states we simulated the control on a shrinking horizon for both, the classic shrinking horizon NMPC (see (3)) and the simplified method represented by Algorithm 1. During the simulations, we evaluated the success rate of the active set predictions under the influence of additive disturbances, i.e., we counted the number of time steps in which the optimal input signal resulted from solving the simplified NLP (12). Furthermore, we monitored the number of iterations performed by the solver to determine the optimal input signals.

TABLE 1 System parameters for (14).

parameter	value	parameter	value	parameter	value
c_1	-1.2776	c_4	-0.0012	c_7	-6.1535
c_2	-0.4412	c_5	0.3605	c_8	-0.0227
c_3	-0.138	c_6	1.5206	c_9	2.0115

The starting horizon length was chosen as $\hat{N} = 15$ for both examples, thus the control of the shrinking horizon NMPC schemes end with $k = \hat{N}$ and $N = 1$, resulting in 15 NLPs to be solved for each of the 500 initial states. All simulations were performed using Matlab2021a using the nonlinear optimizer `fmincon`. For both, Example 1 and 2, we used the interior-point algorithm of `fmincon` to solve the full and simplified NLPs. During the simulations, in every time step, a vector $w(k)$ with randomly chosen, independent values ranging within the constraints specified for each example was added to the resulting successor state to simulate uncertainties.

We did not account for disturbances explicitly in the formulation of problem (2), as the implementation of the approach for a robust NMPC scheme is a further field of research. For a real application, appropriate methods to handle infeasibility, such as, e.g., constraint softening could be useful to deal with disturbances but were not considered for the simulation study since it focuses on the prediction of active sets. Thus, some initial states became infeasible during simulations because of the disturbance, which we excluded from the analysis since these became infeasible for both, the classic and the proposed shrinking horizon NMPC scheme.

Figure 2 shows the closed-loop state and input results for Example 2 and one of the 500 initials values, as well as the number of iterations performed by `fmincon` to determine an optimal input signal $u^*(0)$. For this example and using the proposed approach, only the first NLP had to be solved as a full NLP, while a solution solving the simplified NLP as proposed in Algorithm 1, lines 5 – 7, could be derived for all subsequent time steps. Thus, for the initial state $x(0) = (-4.9551, 1.8125, 3.9132, -2.5983)^\top$, all predicted active sets for the subsequent time steps belonged to an optimal solution, yielding a success rate of 100% for this example simulation. Furthermore, Figure 2 reveals that in all subsequent time steps, i.e., whenever solving the simplified NLP (12) yielded the optimal input signal, the number of iterations performed by `fmincon` could be reduced, while the proposed method still resulted in the same optimal solution sequence as the classic NMPC scheme.

For the simulation setup of 500 initial states and a starting horizon length of $\hat{N} = 15$, in sum at least 7500 NLPs have to be solved for each example. Assuming a success rate of 100% in predicting the active sets for all initial states despite additive disturbances, 7000 simplified NLPs would be solved to determine an optimal input signal. According to Algorithm 1, the first NLP of all 500 initial states needs to be solved as full NLP such that a prediction for the subsequent time step is possible. Thus, the number of time steps in which the solution of the simplified NLP provided an optimal input signal can serve as a measure for the success rate of the active set predictions under the influence of disturbances.

Table 2 summarizes how many input signals were provided by the solution of full and simplified NLPs, respectively, for a shrinking horizon NMPC scheme implemented as proposed by Algorithm 1. For Example 1, in 6964 out of the 7000 possible time steps the optimal input signal was determined by solving the simplified NLP, resulting in a success rate of the active set predictions despite the influence of disturbances of around 99.5%. The success rate for Example 2 is quite similar. Here, 6932 out of 7000 simplified NLPs resulted in the optimal input signal used for control, resulting in a success rate of around 99.0%.

The results of the simulation study in terms of the computational effort for both examples under the influence of disturbances are summarized in Table 3. We compare the average number of iterations performed to solve all problems from starting horizon $N = \hat{N}$ to $N = 1$ for both, the regular shrinking horizon NMPC scheme (classic) and by exploiting the structure of the active

TABLE 2 Robustness of active set predictions against additive disturbances in terms of solved simplified NLPs using the method described by Algorithm 1.

	full NLPs	simplified NLPs	prediction success rate
Example 1	536	6964	99.5%
Example 2	568	6932	99.0%

FIGURE 2 Comparison of state trajectory (upper plot), input sequence (middle plot), and number of iterations performed to find an optimal solution for shrinking horizon NMPC without (color) and with (black) applying Algorithm 1.

sets to simplify the corresponding NLPs (method). In case the full NLP had to be solved as a fallback because no optimal input signal could be determined from solving the simplified NLP (see line 11 in Alg. 1), we summed up the number of iterations performed by both optimizations.

For the bilinear system described by Example 1, on average around 14.2 iterations were performed by `fmincon` to determine an optimal input signal. Exploiting the active set predictions as described in Algorithm 1, the number of iterations decreased on average to around 9.9, resulting in a reduction of around 30.3%. For the fourth-order system described by Example 2, around 14.8 percent of iterations could be saved on average, from around 13.5 iterations for the classic scheme to around 11.5 iterations performed using Algorithm 1.

As only a locally optimal solver was used during runtime, several minima can occur for the same initial value. Furthermore, the full NLP can obviously result in a different active set than anticipated due to the influence of disturbances. However, as long as an optimal solution to (12) was found that fulfills all of the originally posed constraints and the end of the horizon could be reached by solving the resulting simplified NLP, this solution is as valuable as the original (classic) one resulting from solving (3).

We stress that the proposed method does not reduce the worst-case computational effort. However, especially for embedded controller hardware, the energy consumption strongly depends on the overall computation time which usually correlates with the number of iterations that are required to solve an optimization problem (see Sec. 5.2 in Ref. 34 for an evaluation of the impact the computation time can have on the overall energy consumption of a microcontroller). Thus, it is beneficial to also reduce the average computational effort whenever possible to reduce the required energy to run the controller hardware.

TABLE 3 Average number of iterations to determine an optimal control signal for both, the classic and modified NMPC scheme.

	classic	method	reduction in %
Example 1	14.2	9.9	30.3
Example 2	13.5	11.5	14.8

5 | CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

While the resulting structure of the set of active sets on a receding horizon was recently presented for linear MPC, the extension to the nonlinear case is a current field of research. In this article, we showed that for a shrinking horizon a certain structure of the active sets exists also for nonlinear MPC. In fact, the principle of optimality is not only visible in the optimal input sequence but can be transferred to the development of active sets revealing similar structures as for the linear counterpart.

We investigated the robustness of the enabled active set predictions on a shrinking horizon against additive disturbances and applied the insights to an easy-to-implement simplification approach. For two example systems of different complexity we could show that in more than 99% of all cases the predicted active set resulted in an optimal solution. Furthermore, by implementing the simplification approach, savings in terms of the number of iterations performed by the solver to determine an optimal input signal between around 15% and 30% could be achieved.

Future work will focus on identifying configurations of NMPC for which the structure of active sets can also be exploited on a receding horizon as it is possible for the linear case. Robust schemes combined with the proposed method to make the resulting active sets accounting for the expected disturbances will also be investigated.

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Author contributions

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no potential conflict of interests.

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